

Time, speed, mathematics education and society: Questions that arise from assessment

Nikos Makrakis, University of Klagenfurt, ✉ nemakrakis@gmail.com

Time and emphasis on speed shape mathematics teaching, learning and assessment. Although they play an important role, this is not always reflected in research. I use two examples from the strictly timed and high-stakes tests of Greek National Exams in order to try and raise questions about these issues. How do time restrictions and how does emphasis on speed affect Mathematics education and assessment? How can the timed conditions of a mathematics tests affect students in different ways? What role does this emphasis play on the social and political dimension of mathematics education? I will attempt some initial reflections on these questions as well.

Why time?

In the last decades mathematics education research has tried to broaden its lenses. Social, cultural and political aspects are studied now in more ways and different points of focus have emerged. Mathematics education is being studied both as a social activity that is shaped by social conditions and as an activity that shapes our social reality. The study of the relation between mathematics education and our view of reality can be extended to our view of time.

Time is a dimension of mathematics education which is associated with many important aspects of it in teaching, learning and assessment. However, the importance that time plays in mathematics education and the emphasis that it has on speed are not adequately reflected in research. I will draw from the literature on the role of time in education, in order to raise and reflect on questions about the role of time in mathematics education and, especially, in mathematics assessment. How do time and emphasis on speed affect mathematics assessment? How can the timed conditions of mathematics tests affect students in different ways? Which questions does this study of time raise about the social and political dimension of mathematics education?

How does time shape education?

Time is a subjective experience as has been long analysed by philosophy, psychology and sociology of time (e.g., Adam, 1990; Meissner, 2007). In education, time has been studied already by Jean-Jacques Rousseau who “criticized time management in pedagogy” (Pourkos & Kontopodis, 2005, p. 252).

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Even the most cursory look at contemporary school life reveals that everything is timed. It demonstrates that the activities and interactions of all its participants are choreographed to a symphony of buzzers and bells, timetables, schedules, and deadlines. Layer upon layer of such schedules form the structure of our education system. [...]. The beginning and end of lessons, the term, the school year, and the dates and times for tests and exams are some of the fixed points within which subjects, teachers' activities and pupils' expected progress are programmed (Ball et al., 1984; Delamont & Galton, 1986). Within the overall structure of finite time resources and nested timetables, activities are scheduled for pre-set durations. They are structured to follow certain sequences and to happen at a specific rate, at a particular time in the children's lives, over a fixed period, and for a set number of times (Adam, 1990, pp. 105–106).

The everyday school life of teacher and students is bound together by the time schedule. Every activity is very strictly organised in separate time slots, during which students and teachers are supposed to express a very specific behaviour. The time of students' play is very strictly separated from the time of the students' learning and this is signalled by the loud sound of the bell (Adam, 1990; Foucault, 1977).

How does time shape mathematics education?

Time has been studied specifically in mathematics education research, as well (Staats & Laster, 2019). In classrooms there is always a sense of hastiness towards the completion of the prescribed syllabus (e.g., Kolloosche, 2017, p. 1010; Walkerdine, 2013, p. 240) and this can cause students to feel pressure and develop phenomena of math anxiety (Boaler, 2014; Engle, 2002) or mathematics refuse (Chronaki & Kolloosche, 2019).

Not many aspects of time in mathematics education have been studied, like how teachers' waiting time in mathematics classroom discourse improves the length and quality of students' responses (Tobin, 1986) and what is the role of silence (Boistrup, 2010). But, important questions which have been raised by researchers on the role of time concerning the social dimension of mathematics education and assessment have not been studied adequately (Walen & Williams, 2002).

How does time shape mathematics assessment?

Assessment in education is commonly based on students' performance in given amounts of time. The time to be spent at each task is predetermined and students are pressured to perform at a certain pace (Adam, 1990).

Timed conditions of mathematics tests seem to have more negative effects on students than tests for other school subjects (Mollenkopf, 1950). Strictly timed conditions of mathematics tests may block the working memory, cause traumatic experiences to students and math anxiety (Boaler, 2014; Bosmans & De Smedt, 2015). Walen and Williams (2002) suggest that the type of anxiety when a student faces a mathematics test may be distinct from math anxiety or even test anxiety. Emphasis on speed in assessment affects students' view of mathematics, may emphasise blind memorising and makes them think that their object is not to "learn" mathematics, but to know how to "perform" mathematics (Boaler, 2014, pp. 470).

Researchers have compared the performance of different groups of students, according to their math anxiety levels, both in timed and in untimed conditions. Some studies suggest that timed mathematics tests have more negative effects on the performance of high-anxious students than low-anxious ones compared to untimed tests (Hembree, 1987; Tsui & Mazzocco, 2006; Gallagher, 1989; Plass & Hill, 1986; Onwuegbuzie & Seaman, 1995). However, there are other studies which suggest that they could not find statistically significant differences between students' performances under strictly timed or not conditions and, therefore, timed mathematics tests can be considered reliable (Mollenkopf, 1950; Bosmans & De Smedt, 2015; Kellogg et al., 1999). But these studies present methodological issues like small samples (although the one of Onwuegbuzie and Seaman has too). Moreover, all these studies are quantitative and they may miss discussing some important aspects of the effect of timed conditions on students. How does the timed condition of a test affect students in different ways and how can this change the characteristics of the test considerably? Does this raise equity issues (Walen & Williams, 2002)?

Studying these questions, I will examine two examples from timed mathematics tests. I will approach them in a theoretical consideration that regards mathematics assessment activities as acts that constitute discursive frameworks in which students and teachers develop subjective positions (Boistrup, 2010). Boistrup describes four types of assessment discourses in mathematics, one of those called "Do it quick and do it right" (p. 166). This type of discourse emphasises getting the work done fast and giving the right answer regardless of the mathematical processes that have to take place in-between. Developing an analysis on those mathematical processes and this discursive framework is important for our understanding of assessment.

Also, my theoretical approach views logical thinking as intertwined with time, namely that there is the dimension of logical time, described in Lacanian psychoanalysis (Lacan, 2006). When completing a test, the student is not alone, but in an interactive and dialogic situation with the designers of the test. In such situations the individual develops logical thinking which includes the dimension of developing thoughts in response to the Other's presence in time (Lacan, 1993). So, a student faces a mathematics test constantly negotiating the imaginary position of what they should do ahead of what they think that it is expected of them to do, namely in a dialectical and retroactive way and not as a static text.

Example 1: Possible paths in a timed test and luck

This example has to do with the Greek National Exams, which is a high-stakes, nation-wide, 3-hour exam that determines students' entry to higher education (also discussed in Makrakis, 2019). I will take as an example task $\Delta 4$ of the exams of June 2018:

Let function $f(x) = 2e^{x-\alpha} - x^2$, $x \in \mathbb{R}$ & $\alpha > 1$.

$\Delta 4$. If $\alpha=2$ prove: $\int_2^3 f(x)\sqrt{x-2}dx > -\frac{32}{15}$ (Greek Ministry of Education, 2018)

Students have been trained according to their syllabus to know that there are six main ways for them to prove an inequality, which are shown in the first column of Table 1.

Proof method	Inequality for the function f in $[2, 3]$	$\int_2^3 f(x)\sqrt{x-2}dx > \dots$
Monotonicity	$x \leq 2 \Leftrightarrow f(x) \geq f(2) \Rightarrow \boxed{f(x) \geq -2}$	$\int_2^3 (-2)\sqrt{x-2}dx = -1, \bar{3}$
Extremum	$\boxed{f(x) \geq f(x_0)}$	-
Concavity and tangent line at $x_0 = 2$	Tangent for $x=2$: $y = -2x + 2 \rightarrow$ f convex in $[2, 3] \Rightarrow \boxed{f(x) \geq -2x + 2}$	$\int_2^3 (-2x + 2)\sqrt{x-2}dx = -2, 1\bar{3}$
Concavity and tangent line at $x_0 = 3$	Tangent for $x=3$: $y = (2e - 6)x - 4e + 9 \rightarrow f$ convex in $[2, 3] \Rightarrow$ $\boxed{f(x) \geq (2e - 6)x - 4e + 9}$	$\int_2^3 [(2e - 6)x - 4e + 9]\sqrt{x-2}dx \approx -2, 2253 \dots$
Mean value theorem and monotonicity of f	$\exists \xi \in (2, x): f'(\xi) = \frac{f(x)+2}{x-2}$ and f increasing $\Rightarrow \boxed{f(x) > -4x + 6}$	$\int_2^3 (-4x + 6)\sqrt{x-2}dx = -2, 9\bar{3}$
Known inequality $e^x \geq x + 1$	$e^x \geq x + 1 \Rightarrow 2e^{x-2} \geq 2x - 2$ $\Rightarrow \boxed{f(x) \geq -x^2 + 2x - 2}$	$\int_2^3 (-x^2 + 2x - 2)\sqrt{x-2}dx \approx -2, 419 \dots$

Table 1: Possible methods to prove an inequality

After constructing the initial inequality, students would have to multiply by $\sqrt{x-2}$, then to apply a known proposition in order for the integral to appear. This result might or might not lead to the desired inequality. The possible results of this are shown in the third column of Table 1.

Of all six initial methods, the only one that can be excluded early on is the one that uses the extremum, due to the monotonicity of the function, so only five remain. There is no rational way for a student to choose one or exclude one more. All five methods seem equally possible to solve the problem. So, a student cannot know beforehand which method can solve the problem.

Only two methods can, finally, solve the problem. These are the one that uses the monotonicity of the function (second row) and the one that uses the concavity of the function and its tangent line at $x_0 = 2$ (fourth row). The only one that produces the exact outcome is the last one and is, of course, the answer which the designers of the test anticipated that the students would give.

Since a student cannot know from the beginning which method to use so that to solve the problem, a student can choose only by luck. The probability of choosing a correct method is 40%, since there are five methods, of which only two produce the required outcome. A student can know if the method that he or she has chosen is correct only at the very end, namely after computing the last integral.

But a student that has chosen an incorrect method does not have the time to start using another one to solve the problem, because developing one of the methods takes very much time and these integrals require lots of arithmetical computations, as did the whole test. Mathematics tests of the Greek National Exams are, usually, so strictly timed that even experienced teachers would sometimes find it hard to complete them in time (Mavrogiannis, 2017). And no calculator, no graphic calculator and no other tool is allowed. Even if we suppose that a student could find the time to develop another method until the end, then the possibility of them choosing a correct one the second time is only 50% (two out of four). So, we may say that strictly timed math tests which emphasize speed can increase the factor of sheer luck in assessment.

Example 2: Possible paths in a timed test and how making a mistake can save you

Greek National Exams are considered so important that they are designed during the very night prior to the assessment by a secret and small group of people, in order for the test not to be leaked. This time pressure makes errors in the tests possible and they have happened sometimes, e.g., in 2003, 2006, 2011, 2013, 2014 and other years. Rhoades & Madaus (2003) name a category of errors in assessment tests as “latent”, because they happen not just by a random mistake, but because of structural reasons that have to do with the designing of the text and educational policy.

Let us consider the following example from the Greek national exams of May 2003. Task 4 describes a function f . Then, question 4γ asks the students to prove that the function has at least one inflection point (Greek Ministry of Education, 2003).

This task has a serious mathematical error. It is not possible to prove that there is an inflection point with the given data. It can only be proven that there is a value x_0 with $f''(x_0) = 0$, but it cannot be proven that the second derivative is positive to its left and negative to its right, or vice versa. This can only prove a possible inflection point, which is not what the test asked. Finally, despite the obvious error, the commission of the exams decided to give full marks to the answer that proves only a possible inflection point.

Figure 1: Possible approaches by the students

What would a student think when faced with such a task? We could sketch possible thought paths like in Figure 1. Group B mistakenly believe that the answer which they present is a correct one to the problem, as it is posed. Group A is the only one that have a mathematically correct approach to the problem. In the end, Groups A and B give exactly the same solution and obviously get the same marks. What is the difference? Group A needs much more time to think, compute and check all different paths that could solve the problem, as they know that they do not get the result which is asked. This, of course, can have a very harmful effect on their achievement at the other tasks of the test.

Group A follow a better approach as they know that what they have found is not a sufficient proof of what is asked, but they have a bigger chance to fail the test due to the amount of time that they have to spend. The fact that Group B is mistaken in thinking that their answer is correct, is the one that saves them a lot of time, and, consequently, this misrecognition gives them a bigger chance to succeed in the test. We are facing the paradoxical fact that, when solving this task, the better you are at doing mathematics, the worse you are probably expected to perform, because the test is timed.

Questions that the issue of time raises about the socio-political perspectives of mathematics education

We can say that strictly timed mathematics assessment tests have the problem of not assessing the content of mathematics as much as we may think. They increase the factor of luck considerably. Further, during a mathematics test, the development of different paths may result in very different performance outcomes, but these outcomes may not have to do with mathematics itself as much as we imagine.

Are these timed tests designed so strictly that the actual time to complete is inadequate by mistake or on purpose? If some of them are structured in this way by mistake, then how can a mathematics test designer calculate the time needed for a student to complete a task? Literature on this subject is very inadequate.

This ambiguity leads us to additional questions. Do mathematics education policy makers, test designers and teachers value speed as a skill of mathematical literacy to be assessed by a mathematics test? No official agent, that I know of, lists speed as a skill of mathematical literacy for the public education to teach and to assess, especially not OECD (2003), NCTM (2000), EU (The Council of European Union, 2018) or Ministries of Education (Greek Minister of Education, 2015).

If we do not consider speed a skill of mathematical literacy, then why do we assess it? As long as we assess speed, why is this not reflected in mathematics education research and why do we not talk about it or study it? Do we, actually, have a latent appreciation of speed as a skill of mathematical literacy but avoid talking about it? What does this void say about the social and political dimension of Mathematics education? Is there a critical stance on this issue?

Initial thoughts about some directions to be studied for answering these open questions include the following three. Firstly, Suurtamm et al. (2016) suggest that mathematics tests

which focus on the mathematical content may be longer and need more time, both from the students to complete and from the teachers to design, especially if they assess problem solving (Walen & Williams, 2002). Time and stress handling is not the only non-content factor that contributes to performance at mathematics tests (Webb, 1992), as Hembree (1987) studies and lists many of them, like test familiarity, the order of the tasks, praising, competition and others. Does large scale and high-stakes testing make it difficult for a test that focuses on mathematical content to be designed, completed and scored in a desirable time frame? Is the tendency towards standardised testing in mathematics related to that aspect?

Secondly, in mathematics education we prefer discursive norms and rituals which we are familiar with (Lundin & Christensen, 2017) and these make unclear what is mathematical and what is social. So, a student working at a certain familiar and desired pace and speed may seem as fitting a kind of ritual in our minds. Being quick at doing mathematics is sometimes attributed by society to power and masculinity (Bibby, 2010). Ultimately, mathematics education plays an important role for the formation of the subjects and citizens in contemporary neoliberal society (Valero, 2018) as governable subjects (Kollosche, 2018). Is the strictly-timed framework of mathematics education a contribution to the construction of citizens who always hurry and give emphasis on efficiency (Chronaki, 2017, p. 427) and progress (Llewellyn, 2016)?

Thirdly, research suggests that assessment sometimes does not emphasise the mathematical content, but the applicability of statistical tools with the goal to distribute students into a pre-given spectrum of performances (Webb, 1992). So, in the process of designing a test, the time limit becomes a tool for broadening this spectrum of performances and so delivering this goal more adequately. Is this a contribution to one of the social functions of education in a class society, namely to distribute students into the layers of the social division of labor (Althusser, 2014), with exclusion being a structural part of that function (Pais, 2014)?

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Time, speed, mathematics education and society: Questions that arise from assessment

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